

A LOOK AT DETERMINATION AND GOALS OF EXECUTIVE COMPENSATION IN ORGANIZATIONS

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Abstract

This work provides an overview of determination and goals of executive compensation. Compensation management is based on a well-articulated philosophy that is, a set of beliefs and guiding principles that are consistent with the values of the organization and help to enact them. These include beliefs in the need to achieve fairness, equity, consistency and transparency in the reward system. The philosophy recognizes that if human resource management is about investing in human capital from which a reasonable return is required, then it is proper to compensate people differentially according to the contribution, that is, the return on investment they generate. The present study employed literature review survey to gather information on executive compensation which was qualitatively analyzed. The research observed that extremely executive compensation compared with the wages being earned by lower level participants in organizations have led to perception of unfairness and low distributive justice. The study recommend that extremely high executive

compensation should be reduced for pay equity and justice with lower-level workers.

Key Words: Determination, Goals, Chief, Executive, Officer, Management, Organization, Manager, Workers.

Introduction

For more than fifty years, a spring issue of Business Week has reported on executive pay at publicly held companies. In addition to reporting executive pay Business Week also rates the performance of these companies for the most recent years and the often tenuous links between company performance and chief executive officer (CEO) pay. For some years of this survey, most readers, and others, were not overly concerned with executive pay (Okere, 2019). Until recently, people were interested and even envious, but most understood that these executives represented a special resource to organization because of their potential to influence results and hence deserved quite high pay (Farnham, 1992; Business Week, 1994; Business Week, 1995). All of this changed in the 1990s when executive pay became a highly charged topic. The reason for the intense interest says' Farnham (1992) can be summed up in two words "equity and excess". Also, Louis (2001), Geoffrey (2001), argued that extremely high executive compensation compared with the wages being earned by lower-level participants in organizations have led to perception of unfairness and low distributive justice. Chief executive officer cash compensation increases on average by 18% in 2000, whereas salaried worker pay increased by 4.3% (Louis, 2001).

Determination of Executive Compensation

Who determines the pay of the top people in e publicly help organization? Obviously, it would be a conflict of interest to have the Chief executive officer determine the reward structure for the top executives, including him or herself (Okere, 2019). Most publicly held companies have a compensation committee composed of members of the board of directors who are not officers of the

firm. According to Okere (2019), the compensation committee makes recommendations to the board on overall organizational pay policies, including salaries, incentives and perquisites for top officers. Frequently, the compensation committee seeks advice from consultants who specialize in salary and rewards.

Goals of Executive Compensation

Geoffrey (2001) remarked that “the theory of compensating the top people in an organization is straight-forward: what is in the best interest of the shareholders also should be what brings the greatest reward to the executives. In most organizations, executive pay is not supposed to be based on individual performance measures but rather on unit or organizational performance. The reason is that an executive’s own performance is assumed to be directly reflected in measures of unit or corporate performance. Of course, situations differs but stakeholders want the executives to take the compensation forward, that is, to improve things, both in the short and the long term. This wish translates into executive compensation being based on both short-term incentives, for example, annual bonuses, and long-term ones for example, stock options. Consideration must be given to the structure of the incentive arrangements and the performance measures on which incentive compensation will be based. This, in practice incentives are important in determining executive compensation. However, various performance measures are used to determine payouts, most management incentive plans are “formula-driven” plans based on financial measures such as return on equity, profit before or after taxes, and return on invested capital. However, Jennifer (1997) concluded that these attempts to tie executive compensation to organizational performance have not proved as effective as intended. Jeffrey and Richard (1987), Haire et al (1967), John et al (1986) studies discovered no correlation between a company’s stock performance and its compensation of executives. The proliferation of stock-option grants, combined with the rise of unbelievable retirement deals, sign on bonuses, and ironclad severance packages for Chief executive officers has made a mockery out of attempts to

truly link pay to performance. The result, irrespective of talent or lack thereof, is that virtually all Chief executive officers have seen their net worth rise by at least several million dollars (Business Week, 1995). However, several special considerations complicate the process of determining executive compensation. For example, because executives generally enjoy a high base-salary, compensation arrangements seek to minimize their income tax liability. Attention to tax considerations can make a large difference in the after-tax income of an executive. Another consideration has to do with non-financial executive position (Fisher et al, 2003).

Executive Bonus Plan

Bonuses play an important role in today's competitive executive payment programmes. Charles (1985) found that 92% of manufacturing companies in the United States have annual incentive bonus plans for their managers and executives that varies from an average 57% of salary for Chief executive officers to about 20 to 25% for lower-level executives. This type of incentive is annually a short-term one, that is annual, and based on performance. Fisher et al (2003) observed that there are almost as many bonus systems as there are companies using this form of executive compensation. In some systems, the annual bonus is tied by formulas to objective measures, such as gross or net profits, earnings, share price, or return on investment. Other executive bonus plans are based on the subjective judgement of the board of directors and Chief executive officer. Most complex systems establish certain targets, for example, a 10% increase in corporate earnings from the previous year, and generate a bonus pool after the target is attained. The bonus is then distributed, either in accordance with a present formula or on the basis of subjective judgements. For example, Fisher et al (2003) posit that at Coca-Cola, Chief executive officer Douglas Draft stands to gain \$87.2 million, but only if he manages to increase earnings per share by 20% a year for five years, a task that may be difficult, if not impossible.

Long-Term Incentives

Publicly held organizations have been criticized for their focus on the short-term. To encourage a longer perspective, many boards of directors are adopting programmes of long-term incentives for executives (Fisher et al, 2003). Geoffrey (2001), said that for some years, the proportion of executive pay related to long-term incentives increased fourfold, from 8% to 31% of total compensation. According to Okere (2019), in recent years, stock options accounted for more than 60% of a Chief executive officer's average pay package. Salary and bonus mean less and less, with options being the significant factor. Thus, the most popular approach is to give stock options to executives. The options are valuable as long as the price of the stock keeps increasing. However, the stock purchased, or the right to buy stock, can decrease in value and even become worthless, if the company goes bankrupt. Executives of many large companies have suffered this fate in some recent years. Stock options as suggested by Louis (2001) are also attractive to shareholders. First, an option is not a bonus. Executives must use their own resources to exercise their right to purchase the stock. Second, the executives are assuming the same risk as all other stakeholders, such as the price could move in either direction. Options are a form of profit sharing that links the executives financial success to that of the shareholders. Finally, stock options are one of the few ways to offer large rewards to executives without the embarrassment of millions of dollars of obvious money changing hands (Jane, 1989). Nevertheless, the risk factor in this type of incentive may be too great for it to be attractive to executives.

Perquisites

Perquisites, better known as "PEAKS" are the extras that frequently go with executive status. Used to supplement the basic benefit package, perks range from such amenities as special parking and plush offices to pay for vacation travel, automobile expenses, and company-paid memberships in clubs (Fisher et al, 2003). More personal perks, such as low-cost loans and personal use of company facilities such as airplanes, have been slowly disappearing over the last years as various tax and regulatory agencies have ruled that their value

must be included in the executive's taxable income (Geoffrey, 2001). However, the list of perks offered is long and will remain an expected feature of the upper levels of the executives ladder.

Reforming Executive Compensation

John (1992) posit that “we are entering a new era in executive compensation, in which companies increasingly will have to sell their executive-pay programmes to stakeholders”. Having a committee of shareholders develop a plan that combines salary, annual bonus for short-term performance, and long-term stock options sound like a good way to align executive interests with those of critical constituencies, including shareholders, the investment community, and employees (Geoffrey, 2001). In the past years, however, there have been several reasons that this approach has not worked as envisioned. Okere (2019), argued that frequently, the members of the board of directors, including those serving on the compensation committee, are not independent. This lack of independence can have several causes. For instance, members of the board may be appointed by the chairman and Chief executive officer. Or the members of the board may be attorneys or investment bankers who receive fees from the company. It is not unusual for a Chief executive officer to have the Chief executive officer of another company on the board and, in turn, serve on the other Chief executive officer's board. All this according to Business Week (1992) leads to potential conflicts of interest. It appears that research on the role of the board of directors and Chief executive officer salary is mixed. Charles and Phillip (1991) in a study showed that the longer the tenure of the Chief executive officer, the less of a link between compensation and company performance, that is, as a result of the Chief executive officer's ability to build influence within the board and use this influence to weaken incentive alignment mechanisms. Also Catherine et al (1998), found that no evidence that director independence, or lack thereof, led to greater levels of, or changes in, Chief executive officer compensation. The researchers argued that directors, regardless of their level of independence, are ever mindful of their obligations to shareholders. Perhaps this is reinforced by David et al (1998)

study which showed that Chief executive officer compensation in companies whose stock is popular with institutional investors, for example large mutual or pension funds, tends to be more in line with shareholders preferences. As extremely large investors or shareholders, institutional investors pressure the board of directors to do what is right with respect to Chief executive officer compensation. Research has reported that incentives are frequently not what they seem (Okere, 2019). Whereas shareholders have something at risk, namely, their investment in purchasing the shares, many of the forms of long-term incentives and options offered to executives have only upside potential. For example, Graef (1989), pointed out that stock appreciation rights and restricted stock require no investment or risk. In other cases, boards have been known to reprice stock options to allow executives to reap benefits even though performance targets were not realized (Shaifali, 1997). Carol (2001), opined that all the signs point to heightened sensitivity to executive pay on the part of executives, board members and shareholders. Kevin (1992), reported that many board of directors compensation committees now keep a closer eye on compensation and use the options of independent experts when designing executive compensation systems. Several organizations hold the Chief executive officer's base salary to a multiple of the average worker's salary.

Conclusions

Executives are especially important to organizations and thus usually operate with a somewhat different system of compensation and incentives. Frequently, executive reward packages include bonus plans based on organizational performance and long-term incentives, in the form of stock options. Executives may have perks such as company-paid automobiles, club memberships, and other considerations associated with their role. Executive pay has been criticized as being excessive in amount and inequitable when compared with organizational performance. Furthermore, incentive pay has increased much faster than the pay of the average worker or than inflation.

Recommendations

For fairness and equity, concerning executive compensation the following recommendations are proffered:

1. Extremely high executive compensation should be reduced for equity and justice with lower-level workers pay.
2. Executive pay should not be based on individual performance measures, but rather on unit or organizational performance.
3. Consideration must be given to the structure of the incentive arrangements and the performance measure on which incentive compensation will be based.
4. Bonuses should play important role in today's competitive executive payment programmes.
5. To encourage a longer perspective, boards of directors should adopt programmes of long-term incentives for executives.
6. Organizations can give stock or stock options to executives.
7. Perquisites better known as perks should be used to supplement the basic benefit package that is, amenities such as special parking and phush offices pay for vacation travel, automobile expenses, and company-paid memberships in clubs, in compensating executives.
8. Organizations should have a compensation committee composed of members of the board of directors who are not officers of the company to determine the reward structure of the top executives.
9. Chief executive officers' compensation in companies whose stock is popular with institutional investors, e.g. large mutual or pension funds, should be in line with shareholders preferences
10. Board of directors compensation committees should keep closer eye on compensation and use the opinions of independent experts when designing executive compensation systems.

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